

Layering tailored Shape Memory Alloys into Carbon Fibre-Reinforced Polymer Composites for Enhanced Frontal Impact

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Abstract. The automotive industry's pursuit of lightweight components presents a challenge in balancing weight reduction and structural integrity. Shape Memory Alloys (SMAs) offer a promising solution, capable of altering their properties when triggered, enhancing the crashworthiness of front-end vehicle components such as bumper beams and crash boxes. This research integrates SMA elements into carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP), forming an advanced composite material. To validate this approach, crashworthiness testing will use finite element analysis (FEA) software like LS-DYNA. Physical crash tests, though reliable, are costly and time-consuming. FEA simulations provide a cost-effective, time-efficient alternative, crucial for developing automotive components. LS-DYNA's SMA material data cards will accurately model SMA behavior, aiding in the optimization of these composites. The innovative crash box design, incorporating ten SMA wire layers within CFRP, demonstrates significant improvements: a 79% weight reduction compared to standard steel versions, a 60% decrease in peak force, and a 97% increase in specific energy absorption. This cutting-edge research highlights the potential of SMAs to revolutionize automotive component design, achieving superior performance and efficiency.

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1 Introduction

To optimize the crashworthiness of automotive front-end structures (FES) while reducing weight, various innovative approaches have been proposed. These include material selection, structural modifications, and new element introduction.

[7] replaced steel with aluminum alloy 6060, TRIP800, and DP800 in the bumper, crash box, and front rail, achieving a 10.1% increase in energy absorption and an 11.1% decrease in mass. Carbon fiber-reinforced plastic (CFRP) offers significant potential due to its superior specific stiffness, strength, and fatigue properties compared to metals [1]. CFRP provides advantages such as weight reduction, enhanced crash resistance, and aesthetic appeal.

[9] used CFRP to redesign the crash box, enhancing crashworthiness by 52%. [8] reported increased specific energy absorption with CFRP compared to steel, and [7]

reduced bumper beam weight by 35.57% using CFRP. Material selection is crucial for optimizing crashworthiness and achieving weight reduction, with composite materials enabling weight reductions exceeding 50%[4].

To further enhance FES crashworthiness and reduce weight, integrating shape memory alloys (SMA) like nickel-titanium (NiTi) into the material composition is promising. SMAs revert to their original shape after deformation, improving crash resilience while maintaining weight reduction goals.

Finite element analysis (FEA) software, such as LS-DYNA, offers a cost-effective and efficient alternative to real crash tests, expediting vehicle component development and conserving resources.

2 Methodology

The developed model incorporates a conventional crash box design from [10], using CFRP with integrated shape memory alloy (SMA) wires. CFRP's mechanical properties are specified in Table 1. SMAs are layered at 90 degrees and 0 degrees. At 0 degrees, 5 wires are used per face, resulting in a 2mm total CFRP thickness. Two configurations are tested: one with 10 SMA wires and another with 20 wires per face. NiTi is the selected SMA, with key properties in Table 2.

In LS-DYNA, MAT 54/55 is used for CFRP and MAT 30 for SMA elements. The NiTi SMA is modelled in its austenite phase with a Young's modulus of 83 GPa. A Mesh Sensitivity Analysis determined the optimal element size to be 5 after testing sizes from 2 to 10. The ideal Node Integration Points (NIP) value was found to be 10 through trial and error, testing values from 1 to 15.

Collision simulations use a planar moving forces rigid wall with an 800 kg mass and a velocity of 20 mph [3]. The crash box's opposite end is anchored with specific boundary conditions to prevent movement. Three crash box versions are simulated: a standard steel version (properties in Table 3), a CFRP model with SMA wires on the outer face, and another with SMA wires embedded within the CFRP.

The SMA wires are layered between 1mm CFRP sheets at a 0° angle, contacting both CFRP layers via tied node surface contacts. The CFRP sheets act as solid components with automatic surface-to-surface contact, defined as a single integrated part in LS-DYNA. The simplified collision simulation focuses on the crash box, excluding other components like the bumper beam, to independently assess the effectiveness of the SMA-CFRP layering.

TABLE 1: Material properties of CFRP [5]

Properties	CFRP
Density (kg/mm ³)	1.6x10 ⁻⁶
Longitudinal Young's Modulus (GPa)	70
Transverse Young's Modulus (GPa)	70
Shear Modulus (GPa)	5
Poisson's ratio	0.1

TABLE 2: Material properties of NiTi [7]

Properties	NiTi
Poisson's ratio	0.33
Austenite Young's Modulus (GPa)	83
Martensite Young's Modulus (GPa)	28 - 41
Density (kg/mm ³)	2.7x10 ⁻⁶
Yield Stress (GPa)	1.45

TABLE 3: Material properties of steel [2]

Properties	Steel
Poisson's ratio	0.3
Young's Modulus (GPa)	200
Density (kg/mm ³)	7.83x10 ⁻⁶
Yield Stress (GPa)	0.36

3 Results and Discussion

After comparing the specific energy absorption (SEA) of different quantities of shape memory alloy (SMA) wires, it was concluded that the optimal configuration consists of 10 wires. The 20-wire configuration experienced premature failure due to brittleness and element deletion in the simulation. Despite minimal SEA differences, the 10-wire setup showed better impact endurance. The 20-wire configuration increased peak force by 0.2%, so 10 wires were used for both CFRP designs, with wires layered between the CFRP and on the crash box's outer faces.

The standard steel version showed a peak force of 239.57 kN, reduced by 51% when switched to CFRP with SMA wires on the outer faces (Figure 1). This force was further reduced to 96.47 kN, a 60% decrease, with SMA wires layered within the CFRP structure. The force-displacement curve for layered CFRP showed a gradual increase in force, with the peak occurring at the end of the collision, unlike the other designs where peak force occurred initially. This gradual deceleration improves occupant safety by avoiding sudden jolts.

Specific energy absorption for the three crash box versions was also compared (Figure 2). The CFRP version with SMA on the outer faces increased SEA from 2949.57 J/kg (standard steel) to 84967.74 J/kg, a 96.5% increase. The CFRP crash box with SMA layered between the CFRP materials further improved SEA to 87174.47 J/kg, a 97% increase compared to steel and a 0.5% increase over the non-layered CFRP version. The weight comparison for the three crash box versions showed that the CFRP designs, differing only in SMA integration, had the same weight (figure 3). The weight reduced from 1.75 kg (steel version) to 0.36 kg for CFRP designs, a 79% reduction. A

lighter crash box maintains or enhances energy absorption and crashworthiness, reduces vehicle inertia, improves handling and stability, and lowers rollover risks.

Figure 1: Force against displacement curve for the three version of the crash box simulated.

Figure 2: Specific energy absorption comparison for the three version of the crash box simulated.

Figure 3: Weight comparison for the three version of the crash box simulated.

4 Conclusions

In conclusion, our study examined the specific energy absorption (SEA) of shape memory alloy (SMA) wires in crash box designs. We found that 10 wires was the optimal configuration, as the 20-wire setup experienced premature failure due to material brittleness.

Despite minimal SEA differences, the 10-wire design showed better impact endurance and only a 0.2% increase in peak force compared to the 20-wire configuration. Thus, we chose the 10-wire setup for CFRP-integrated designs.

Force-displacement analysis indicated that CFRP with SMA wires significantly reduced peak forces during collisions. The layered CFRP design showed a gradual force reduction, enhancing occupant safety by avoiding abrupt deceleration.

Comparing SEA, the CFRP version with outer-facing SMA wires increased SEA by 96.5%, and the version with layered SMA wires improved SEA by 97% over the standard steel version. This higher energy absorption reduces impact forces on occupants, promoting road safety.

Both CFRP designs reduced crash box weight from 1.75 kg (steel) to 0.36 kg, a 79% reduction. This weight reduction, while maintaining or improving safety, benefits vehicle dynamics, maneuverability, and rollover prevention.

In summary, layering SMA wires within CFRP crash box designs enhances SEA and reduces weight, offering improved vehicle safety and performance.

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